

Challenges in Implementing English Language Education Curriculum in Universities in The Gambia

Masanneh Jabango CEESAY

Department of Arts and Social Science Education
Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria
massjceesay78@gmail.com

Abstract

This study gathered information about challenges encountered by English Language Education lecturers in both public and private universities in The Gambia and examined the possible or recommended solutions for each of the challenges. This study was meant to promote quality service delivery and enhance the knowledge, skills, and competencies of the concerned lecturers at universities in The Gambia. A developed research instrument; namely, Questionnaire on University Curriculum Implementation Challenges (QUCI), was used to gather data from English Language Education lecturers from both the University of The Gambia (UTG) and the International Open University (IOU). The data collected was analysed using means and standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis. The results showed that the mean score challenges was 152.20 (SD= 20.661), indicating that on average, respondents rated the level of challenges as moderately high. The minimum score was 120, while the maximum score was 188. The standard deviation of 20.661 further confirms a moderate spread in response. Skewness (0.179, SE = 0.580). The skewness value was close to zero, indicating that the data distribution was approximately symmetrical. Kurtosis (-0.829, SE = 1.121). The negative kurtosis value indicated a slightly flatter distribution. The study concluded that the challenges encountered by lecturers in the implementation of English Language Education curriculum were moderate in both universities. It is recommended that both UTG and IOU should address the challenges faced by lecturers in implementing English Language Education curriculum.

Keywords: challenges, Curriculum, English Language Education.

Reference to this paper should be made as follows:

Ceesay, M. J. (2025). Challenges in Implementing English Language Education Curriculum in Universities in The Gambia. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 18(4), 633-642.

Copyright © 2025 IJSRE

INTRODUCTION

Universities in The Gambia place a high value on English language instruction since it is unquestionably essential to giving students the language skills, they need for critical thinking, academic and professional achievement, and international communication. Notwithstanding its

purposes, English Language Education instructors and curricula at universities in The Gambia are facing many challenges that hinder their successful and efficient execution. These challenges range from outdated teaching strategies and a lack of resources to the growing disparity in student proficiency and technology integration. The increasing demand for English proficiency worldwide makes it more important than ever to solve these issues. This study aims to enhance students' educational experiences via curriculum design and delivery at universities in The Gambia.

Teachers are the most crucial element in running the teaching and learning processes (Stronge, 2018); however, it is getting more difficult to achieve successful outcomes when the teachers do not have adequate communication proficiency, which influences the students' high expectations of good learning opportunities, particularly in English Language Teaching (ELT). There is also a gender dimension to this problem; for example, male lecturers face numerous challenges in implementing English Language Education curriculum, as it is always expected of them to be assertive in their teaching styles (Hasibuan & Kardena, 2024; Lestari, 2023). Similarly, if English teachers do not comprehend communicative language teaching philosophies, the accurate sociolinguistic context, and the students' need for language acquisition, it can be a problem in implementing teaching practices (Yulia, 2013).

Educators and students deal with various problems and challenges in language teaching and learning. The issues partly come from students and English teachers (Songbatumis 2017). Despite having learned English for years, plenty of students still find it challenging to communicate with the target language, particularly in speaking, which commonly requires them to transfer their ideas orally and other skills (Abrar et al., 2018). As a result, several students are rarely motivated to study well. Moreover, the students' motivation is an essential part that needs to be developed by the English teachers to involve them in English teaching and learning. Thus, it is one of the challenges for teachers to lead the instruction and interest the students in engaging in the teaching.

In addition, to optimizing language learning, like students' different backgrounds and characteristics that affect their language acquisition, teachers also face many other challenges. Consequently, most students have low proficiency in English language comprehension (Agung, 2019). It occurs because the students have poor vocabulary mastery. Therefore, it becomes an obstacle for teachers to teach the students with appropriate strategies to face this problem. Besides, the problem is also related to the utilization of instructional media such as PowerPoint Presentations. The teachers cannot maximize their use to conduct the teaching and learning process effectively and attractively (Sukmahidayanti, 2015). This happens to the teachers' qualifications who come to teach English without any teaching training. Moreover, teaching English seems to be more challenging when it relates to teachers' problems due to a lack of experience (Karademir & Gorgoz, 2019). Those who did not receive enough teaching training might struggle to utilize the teaching method effectively.

Furthermore, the majority of English teachers are unprepared for the lessons they must provide. As they do not have an English bachelor's degree relevant to teaching primary pupils, their pedagogical understanding may be insufficient for teaching English (Hawanti, 2014). Additionally, inadequate time is another problem in teaching English. The lesson time is frequently limited; once or twice a week, one or two hours every day for various subjects to teach (Hamdan, 2017). As a result, the lesson plan does not go as planned, and the following session would frequently be a review of the previous unfinished teaching-learning materials. To

make matters worse, they will be unable to detect the issues present in the learners' learning process.

Overcrowded English classes are also still one of the biggest problems faced by English teachers, and the effect of such a situation can be seen during the process of teaching and learning (Songbatumis, 2017). An overcrowded class is widely known as one difficulty in teaching English. Consequently, the teacher will find new problems, which include more difficult class management, a noisy class, and the teacher cannot pay attention to each student.

Several teachers are also rarely motivated to teach English due to the curriculum policy's complex demands that limit teachers' activities to serve innovative ideas for good quality language teaching and learning. Due to the short time of teaching, limited facilities, and low salary, some teachers find it challenging to lead the instruction to achieve various indicators proposed in the 2013 curriculum. Meanwhile, the teachers lack knowledge of English Language Teaching (ELT) implementation, as stated in Curriculum 2013 (Apsari, 2018). This also refers to the performance of the scientific approaches and models, including project-based learning, problem-based learning, and discovery learning (Apsari, 2018).

University education in the Gambia started very late, and in fact, it had officially started with the founding of St. Mary's University Extension Programme (UEP) in 1995. This involved the widespread adoption of St. Mary's University Curriculum and the one-sided delivery of university education in The Gambia by St. Mary's University. The Gambia's education, especially at the university level, was far lower than that of other Anglophone West African countries. Before 1960, when the West African Subregion gained independence, practically every country had a reputable university except The Gambia.

English Language Education in The Gambia is very important, and addressing some of the challenges it faces will enhance its overall role in global communication, higher education, and professional settings. If the challenges highlighted above are left unattended, they would have a profound effect on the graduate in terms of gaps in communication skills, problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and the chance of employability of graduates for international and competitive job opportunities.

The main challenges encountered by lecturers of English Language Education at both the University of The Gambia (UTG) and the International Open University (IOU) are: technological, educational, economic, and political, respectively. Technological challenges faced by English Language Education lecturers include but are not limited to: lack of technological infrastructure, high cost of technology, digital divide among students, insufficient technological training for educators, cybersecurity risks, stakeholders' resistance to change, limited access to technology, reliance on technology for assessment, overreliance on technology, and inadequate technological tools. Educational challenges encountered by lecturers of English Language Education are: overcrowded classrooms, inflexible curriculum, high lecturer turnover, insufficient administrative support, misalignment of curricula with standards, inadequate professional development, limited learning resources, inaccessible higher education, unaffordable higher education, and insufficient cooperation among lecturers.

In addition to the above-mentioned challenges, economic and political challenges also affect the efficient and effective implementation of English Language Education curricula in Universities in The Gambia. Economic challenges faced by English Language Education lecturers are: the high cost of learning materials, limited professional development funds, high cost of education, inflexibility in funding allocation, economic disparity among students, rising operational cost, unequal access to higher education, high cost of technology, and poor school

infrastructure. Finally, political challenges affecting the successful implementation of English Language Education curriculum are: the imposition of ideology, administrative delays, corruption among stakeholders, frequent political interference, incoherent educational policies, patronage systems in education, disorganized education coordination, inadequate political will and support, and inconsistent political focus.

Statement of the Problem

There is no gainsaying the fact that since the establishment of university education in The Gambia, there have been challenges in developing and implementing minimum academic benchmarks for universities in The Gambia. Male lecturers in implementing English Language Education curriculum may be expected to take a more authoritative or assertive teaching style, even when a more collaborative or empathetic approach might be more effective. Female lecturers may also face overt or subtle gender bias, including lower pay, fewer promotions, or being overlooked for leadership roles in favor of male colleagues. In summary, in implementing English Language Education curriculum, universities face technological, educational, economic and political challenges. Universities tailor-made degree programmes without being benchmarked against any minimum academic standards. This has therefore led to the emergence of degrees that are being run by universities with different curriculum elements. The contents of similar degree programmes are hugely different and produce graduates with different competencies and skill sets for the job market.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to assess the university curricula of English Language Education in The Gambia. The specific objective of this study is to:

- Examine the challenges encountered by female lecturers in implementing English Language Education curriculum at the two selected universities in The Gambia.

Research Questions

- What is the nature of the challenges encountered by male lecturers in implementing English Language Education curriculum?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design is regarded as an appropriate design for the study because it allows the assessment of curricula, using a predetermined set of questionnaires to collect data on English Language Education programmes in the two selected universities in The Gambia. The population of this study included all twenty (20) lecturers in two universities offering English Language Education in The Gambia. Using a purposive sampling technique, the sample comprised 15 lecturers of English Language Education. Out of the eight (8) universities in The Gambia, the two universities offering English Language Education programme were purposively selected.

Lecturers from the two universities were involved in the sampling process. Using a purposive sample technique, eleven (11) lecturers were selected from the University of The Gambia (UTG), and four (4) lecturers were selected from the International Open University (IOU), respectively. The lecturers selected were those on the ground at the universities at the time of conducting the study. A developed research instrument, namely: Questionnaire on University Curriculum Implementation Challenges (QUCI), was used. This Questionnaire was used to gather information about the challenges of English Language Education curriculum implementation at the two selected universities in The Gambia. The questionnaire was divided into five (5) sections: A, B, C, D, and E. Section A was used to collect the biodata of the university lecturers. Section B was used to gather data on technological challenges encountered by English Language Education lecturers. Section C was used to gather data on educational challenges encountered by English Language Education lecturers. Section D was used to gather data on economic challenges encountered by English Language Education lecturers, and Section E was used to gather data on political challenges encountered by English Language Education lecturers.

The rating scale of sections B, C, D, and E was Very High, High, Fair, Low, Very Low, and Not a Challenge. Permission to collect data was sought from the authorities of the two universities. Two research assistants were trained to guide the respondents in filling out the questionnaire. The questionnaires were administered to the research subjects, and all of them were monitored by the research assistants for proper completion and collection. The data collected was analysed based on the research questions for the study. They were collated, coded, and scored. Descriptive statistics, means, standard deviation, and kurtosis were used to analyse the results.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the nature of challenges encountered by English Language Education lecturers at UTG and IOU?

In order to assess the nature of challenges encountered by English Language Education lecturers at UTG and IOU, descriptive statistics, mean, percentages, and standard deviation were used. The results of the findings are highlighted in Table 1.

Table 1: The Nature of Challenges Encountered by English Language Education Lecturers at UTG and IOU.

	Technological Challenges	VH F(%)	H F(%)	F F(%)	L F(%)	VL F(%)	NC F(%)	Mean	SD
1	Lack of Technological Infrastructure	3(20.0)	7(46.7)	5(33.3)	-	-	-	3.87	.74
2	High Cost of Technology	4(26.7)	9(60.0)	2(13.3)	-	-	-	4.13	.64
3	Digital Divide among Students	7(46.7)	6(40.0)	2(13.3)	-	-	-	4.33	.72
4	Insufficient Technological Training for Educators	4(26.7)	7(46.7)	3(20.0)	1(6.7)	-	-	3.93	.88
5	Cybersecurity Risks	5(33.3)	8(53.3)	2(13.3)	-	-	-	4.20	.68
6	Stakeholders' Resistance to Change	4(26.7)	3(20.0)	6(40.0)	-	1(6.7)	1(6.7)	3.40	1.45
7	Limited Access to Technology	5(33.3)	8(53.3)	2(13.3)	-	-	-	4.20	.68
8	Reliance on Technology for	1(6.7)	3(20.0)	5(33.3)	4(26.7)	1(6.7)	1(6.7)	2.73	1.28

Assessment									
9	Over-reliance on Technology	3(20.0)	1(6.7)	6(40.0)	4(26.7)	1(6.7)	-	3.07	1.22
10	Inadequate Technological Tools	2(13.3)	9(60.0)	4(26.7)	-	-	-	3.87	.64
		Mean aggregate = 3.77		SD = 0.53					
Educational Challenges									
		VH	H	F	L	VL	NC	Mean	SD
		F(%)	F(%)	F(%)	F(%)	F(%)	F(%)		
1	Overcrowded Classrooms	7(46.7)	5(33.3)	3(20.0)	-	-	-	4.27	.80
2	Inflexible Curriculum	4(26.7)	5(33.3)	4(26.7)	1(6.7)	-	1(6.7)	3.60	1.35
3	High Lecturer Turnover	3(20.0)	5(55.3)	5(33.3)	2(13.3)	-	-	3.60	.99
4	Insufficient administrative Support	4(26.7)	4(26.7)	5(33.3)	2(13.3)	-	-	3.67	1.05
5	Misalignment of Curricula with Standards	3(20.0)	5(33.3)	5(33.3)	2(13.3)	-	-	3.60	.99
6	Inadequate Professional Development	4(26.7)	9(60.0)	2(13.3)	-	-	-	4.13	.64
7	Limited Learning Resources	7(46.7)	3(20.0)	5(33.3)	-	-	-	4.13	.92
8	Inaccessible Higher Education	3(20.0)	5(33.3)	5(33.3)	2(13.3)	-	-	3.60	.99
9	Unaffordable Higher Education	4(26.7)	9(60.0)	2(13.3)	-	-	-	4.13	.64
10	Insufficient Cooperation among Lecturers	2(13.3)	4(26.7)	2(13.3)	2(13.3)	5(33.3)	-	2.73	1.53
		Mean aggregate = 3.75		SD = 0.45					
Economic Challenges									
		VH	H	F	L	VL	NC	Mean	SD
		F(%)	F(%)	F(%)	F(%)	F(%)	F(%)		
1	High Cost of Learning Materials	4(26.7)	7(46.7)	4(26.7)	-	-	-	4.00	.76
2	Limited Professional Development Funds	7(46.7)	7(46.7)	1(6.7)	-	-	-	4.40	.63
3	High Cost of Education	3(13.3)	10(66.7)	2(13.3)	-	-	-	4.07	.59
4	Inflexibility in Funding Allocation	4(26.7)	8(53.3)	3(20.0)	-	-	-	4.07	.70
5	Economic Disparity among Students	4(26.7)	8(53.3)	3(20.0)	-	-	-	4.07	.70
6	Poor Remuneration for Lecturers	7(46.7)	7(46.7)	1(6.7)	-	-	-	4.40	.63
7	Rising Operational Cost	4(26.7)	9(60.0)	2(13.3)	-	-	-	4.13	.64
8	Unequal Access to High Education	4(26.7)	6(40.0)	4(26.7)	1(6.7)	-	-	3.80	1.08
9	High Cost of Technology	8(53.3)	6(40.0)	1(6.7)	-	-	-	4.47	.64
10	Poor School Infrastructure	2(13.3)	5(33.3)	5(33.3)	3(20.0)	-	-	3.40	.99
		Mean aggregate = 4.08		SD = 0.32					
Political challenges									
		VH	H	F	L	VL	NC	Mean	SD
		F(%)	F(%)	F(%)	F(%)	F(%)	F(%)		
1	Imposition of Ideology	1(6.7)	5(33.3)	6(40.0)	2(13.3)	1(6.7)	-	3.20	1.01
2	Administrative Delays	1(6.7)	11(73.3)	2(13.3)	1(6.7)	-	-	3.80	.68
3	Corruption among Stakeholders	6(40.0)	3(20.0)	4(26.7)	1(6.7)	1(6.7)	-	3.80	1.27
4	Frequent Political Interference	3(20.0)	4(26.7)	3(20.0)	3(20.0)	2(13.3)	-	3.20	1.37
5	Incoherent Educational Policies	2(13.3)	6(40.0)	5(33.3)	1(6.7)	1(6.7)	-	3.47	1.06
6	Patronage Systems in Education	3(20.0)	8(53.3)	3(20.0)	1(6.7)	-	-	3.87	.83
7	Disorganized Education Coordination	-	8(53.3)	3(20.0)	(20.0)	1(6.7)	-	3.20	1.01
8	Inadequate Funding Allocation	6(40.0)	5(33.3)	4(26.7)	-	-	-	4.13	.83
9	Inadequate Political Will and Support	3(20.0)	8(53.3)	3(20.0)	-	1(6.7)	-	3.80	1.01
10	Inconsistent Political Focus	4(26.6)	6(40.0)	3(20.0)	1(6.7)	1(6.7)	-	3.73	1.16
		Mean aggregate =3.62		SD = 0.33					

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 1 shows the results of technological, educational, economic, and political challenges encountered in the implementation of English Language Education curriculum in UTG and IOU. First, for technological challenges, there is a 6-Likert scale, which means that the benchmark is 3.5. To accept any of the items as a challenge, its mean must be 3.5 or more. From the table, three of the ten items, Insufficient technological training for Educators (mean = 3.40), Reliance on Technology for Assessment (mean = 2.73), and Over-reliance on Technology (mean = 3.07), were not seen as a challenge. The remaining items, therefore, are the challenges faced under technological challenges. They are a Lack of Technological Infrastructure, High Cost of Technology, Digital Divide among Students, Cybersecurity Risks, Stakeholders' Resistance to Change, Limited Access to Technology, and Inadequate Technological Tools. The mean aggregate, 3.77, which is greater than the mean benchmark, implies that the majority of the items are challenges faced under technological challenges.

For educational challenges, there was a 6-Likert scale, which means that the benchmark was 3.5. To accept any of the items as a challenge, its mean must be 3.5 or more. From the table, only item 10, which was Insufficient Cooperation among Lecturers (mean = 2.73), was not considered a challenge. Others like Overcrowded Classrooms, Inflexible Curriculum, High Lecturer Turnover, Insufficient Administrative Support, Misalignment of Curricula with Standards, Inadequate Professional Development, Limited Learning Resources, Inaccessible Higher Education, and Unaffordable Higher Education are considered challenges under educational challenges. The mean aggregate, 3.75, which was greater than the mean benchmark, supports that majority of the items were considered educational challenges.

On economic challenges, there was a 6-Likert scale, which means that the benchmark was 3.5. In order to accept any of the items as a challenge, its mean must be 3.5 or more. From the table, only item 10, which was Poor School Infrastructure (mean = 3.40) was not considered a challenge. Others like High Cost of Learning Materials, Limited Professional Development Funds, High Cost of Education, Inflexibility in Funding Allocation, Economic Disparity among Students, Poor Remuneration for Lecturers, Rising Operational Costs, Unequal Access to Higher Education, and High Cost of Technology. The mean aggregate, 4.08, confirmed that the majority of the items are challenges faced under economic challenges.

Finally, on political challenges, there was a 6-Likert scale, which means that the benchmark is 3.5. To accept any of the items as a challenge, its mean must be 3.5 or more. From the table, items 1, 4, 5, and 7 had means less than 3.5. It followed that the majority of the respondents did not see the Imposition of Ideology, Frequent Political Interference, Incoherent Educational Policies, and Disorganized Education Coordination as challenges. Others like Administrative Delays, Corruption among Stakeholders, Patronage Systems in Education, Inadequate Funding Allocation, Inadequate Political Will and Support, and Inconsistent Political Focus are seen as challenges. The mean aggregate, 3.62, which was greater than the mean benchmark, showed that majority of the items were accepted as challenges under political challenges.

Table 2: The Overall Results on the Nature of Challenges Encountered by English Language Education Lecturers at UTG and IOU

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD.	Skewness	Kurtosis
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
Sum	15	120	188	152.20	20.66	.18	-.83
Valid N (listwise)	15					.58	1.12

Table 2 shows the results of the overall challenge score for English Language Education curriculum implementation, based on the combination of technological, educational, economic, and political challenges, providing insights into the extent and distribution of challenges faced. The mean challenge score was 152.20 (SD = 20.66), indicating that, on average, respondents rated the level of challenges as moderately high. The minimum score recorded was 120, while the maximum was 188, suggesting some variability in how different respondents perceived the challenges. The standard deviation of 20.66 further confirmed a moderate spread in responses. Skewness (0.18, SE = 0.58): The skewness value was close to zero, indicating that the data distribution was approximately symmetrical. This suggested that there was no significant bias toward higher or lower challenge ratings. Kurtosis (-0.83, SE = 1.12): The negative kurtosis value indicated a slightly flatter distribution, meaning responses were somewhat spread out rather than highly concentrated around the mean. The results suggested that challenges in university curriculum implementation are substantial, given the relatively high mean score. The moderate variability in responses indicated that while most participants perceived notable challenges, some rated them lower or higher. The symmetrical distribution suggested that extreme views (very high or very low challenges) were not dominant. The nature of challenges encountered by English Language Education lecturers at the University of The Gambia (UTG) and the International Open University (IOU) was moderate for both universities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings on the challenges encountered by lecturers in the implementation of English Language Education curriculum were the lack of suitable teaching materials and resources that align with the curriculum. This is supported by Richard et al. (2013) that English language learners come from varied linguistic and cultural backgrounds, making it difficult to meet the diverse needs of all students. This requires teachers to adopt flexible and differentiated teaching approaches. Based on the combination of technological, educational, economic, and political challenges, to provides insights into the extent and distribution of challenges faced in the implementation of English Language Education curriculum. This study was able to discover how each of the challenges mentioned above could affect the overall performance of the lecturers and their accompanying effects on quality teaching and learning. This lack of resources made it difficult for the teachers to design engaging and effective lesson plans. Each class has a different way of learning and understanding, so the teacher cannot just use one lesson plan for other classes (Stronge, 2018).

Utami and Hasanah (2020) discovered that the integration of technology in education has been shown to have a positive impact on student outcomes, including improved academic performance, increased motivation, and better preparation for the workforce. Another challenge was the difficulty in assessing student learning outcomes in English Language Education. Therefore, more effective assessment tools and strategies to evaluate student learning are required.

In his research, Stronge (2018) discovered that lecturers faced the challenge of navigating the wide range of available learning media platforms, with many of them struggling to operate and effectively utilize them. Furthermore, the findings showed that the lecturers struggled to integrate technology into their English language teaching practices. Therefore, limited access to technology, inadequate technological tools, and the lack of required expertise to operate them

affect the effective and efficient implementation of English Language Education curriculum in both UTG and IOU. The findings of this study highlight the need for the government of The Gambia, through the Ministry of Higher Education, Research, Science and Technology (MoHERST), to provide more support and resources to teachers to facilitate the implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum. This includes providing training and guidance on how to teach using the new curriculum, as well as providing access to resources and infrastructure that support technology-enhanced learning

Furthermore, the findings showed that some lecturers struggled to adapt to the student-centered approach of the English Language Education Curriculum. The English Language Education curriculum incorporates the innovative approach of differentiated instruction, which involves tailoring teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of students, as advocated by researchers such as Apsari (2018).

This study concludes that, in the field of teaching English as a foreign language, educators frequently face numerous challenges stemming from various factors such as technological, educational, economic, and political. This is supported by Utami and Hasanah (2020) that one obstacle that hinders teachers in achieving learning objectives is related to the implementation of the curriculum in educational institutions. When implementing a curriculum, teachers may face two distinct types of challenges: internal and external. Internal barriers stem from the teachers themselves, while external barriers are linked to factors such as students, learning facilities, educational institutions, or the government. By identifying and addressing these challenges, schools and relevant stakeholders can assist teachers in delivering high-quality instruction and ensuring that all students can attain their learning objectives.

CONCLUSION

The research findings show that the challenges encountered by lecturers in the University of The Gambia (UTG) and the International Open University (IOU) in the implementation of English Language Education curriculum were similarly moderate in both universities.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the research, the following recommendations were made:

- For improved curriculum design, teaching quality, and accreditation requirements, the government of The Gambia should sign a memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with universities in Africa and beyond for support.
- The government of The Gambia should increase funding for the professional development of English Language Education lecturers to keep them abreast with the contemporary teaching techniques, methods, and technological integration.
- English Language Education lecturers should explore creative methods of delivering content, such as using technology, blended learning approaches, and real-world applications of language skills, to make learning more engaging and effective for students.
- The University of The Gambia (UTG) and International Open University (IOU) should both address the challenges faced by their lecturers in implementing the curriculum. This

could involve workshops on innovative teaching techniques, student-centered learning, and the integration of technology in language teaching.

REFERENCES

- Abrar, M., Mukminin, A., Habibi, A., Asyraf, F., Makmur, M., & Marzulina, L. (2018). If English isn't a language, what is it? Indonesian EFL student teachers' challenges speaking English. *The Qualitative Report*, 23(1), 129-145.
- Agung, A. S. N. (2019). Current challenges in teaching English in the least-developed region in Indonesia. *Journal Social dan Humaniora*, 9(3), 266-271.
- Apsari, Y. (2018). Teachers' problems and solutions in implementing curriculum 2013. *Acuity: Journal of English Language Pedagogy, Literature and Culture*, 3(1), 11-23.
- Hamdan, M. H. (2017). Investigating the Saudi EFL trainee students' satisfaction with the English practicum program. *International Journal of English Language and Linguistics Research*, 5(1), 31-57.
- Hasibuan, R. A., & Kardena, A. (2024). English teachers' challenges in implementing Merdeka Curriculum. *PESHUM: Jurnal Pendidikan, Sosial dan Humaniora*, 3(4), 602-606.
- Hawanti, S. (2014). Implementing Indonesia's English language teaching policy in primary schools: The role of teachers' knowledge and beliefs. *International Journal of Pedagogies and Learning*, 9(2), 162-170.
- Karademir, C. A., & Gorgoz, S. (2019). English teachers' problems encountered in teaching four basic language skills. *International Education Studies*, 12(4), 118-127.
- Lestari, I. (2023). The English teacher's perspective and challenge on implementing Merdeka curriculum. *RETORIKA: Jurnal Ilmu Bahasa*, 9(3), 331-339.
- Richard, E., Reitz, C., Honig, L. H., Schupf, N., Tang, M. X., Manly, J. J., ... & Luchsinger, J. A. (2013). Late-life depression, mild cognitive impairment, and dementia. *JAMA Neurology*, 70(3), 383-389.
- Stronge, J. H. (2018). *Qualities of effective teachers*. ASCD. Library of Congress Cataloging in Publication Data.
- Sukmahidayanti, T. (2015). The utilization of instructional media in teaching English to young learners. *Journal of English and Education*, 3(1), 20-27.
- Songbatumis, A. M. (2017). Challenges in teaching English faced by English teachers at MTsN Taliwang, Indonesia. *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Learning*, 2(2), 54-67.
- Utami, P. T., & Hasanah, N. (2020). Good teacher, qualified teacher, and professional teacher: Facing the 21st century global changes. *Ahmad Dahlan Journal of English Studies*, 7(1), 55.
- Yulia, Y. (2013). Teaching challenges in Indonesia: Motivating students and teachers' classroom language. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 3(1), 1-16.